

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO YOUNG CHILDREN

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Annotation : This article discusses the methods of teaching a foreign language to young children and the methods of language teaching at the same time.

Key words : foreign languages , general education , communication , Methodologically poorly

After our country gained independence, great attention has been paid to learning foreign languages in our country. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012, and the introduction of foreign languages in the first classes of general education schools from the 2013-2014 school year. the introduction of continuous training is proof of this.

Nowadays, foreign language, especially English, is taught not only to students of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities, but also to students of preschool education centers and employees working in various fields. There's a reason for that, of course. Learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally developed countries is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development.

Language learning also depends on age periods. According to psychologists, children learn language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of learning a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest.

Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible. The following methods can be used to teach children English in a meaningful and interesting way:

- to teach by means of songs and poems the letters or combinations that are difficult to explain or remember, that do not have meaning. For example, it can be shown that children learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing it.
- games related to mental and physical activities;

- cartoons; While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

- role play, the teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: a student howls a dog, meows a cat

shows, another student needs to find out which animal these sounds belong to and say its English name.

Another reason why it is better to start learning a foreign language at preschool age is that the younger the child, the less vocabulary he has a small child has fewer areas of communication than adults, he does not yet have to solve complex communication problems. This means that when he learns a foreign language, he will not notice a huge difference between the opportunities in his mother tongue and foreign languages, and his feelings of success will be brighter. requires a completely different methodological approach. Methodologically poorly organized English language classes in pre-school educational institutions can create in children a long-term hatred of the foreign language and lack of confidence in their abilities. Only experienced professionals should work with preschool children.

In the preschool age, during the teaching of English, children gradually develop the basics of communicative competence, which includes the following aspects at the initial stage of learning English:

- step by step formation of the ability to repeat correctly from a phonetic point of view, that is, to pronounce English words correctly after the teacher;
- mastering, combining and activating English words;
- mastering a certain number of simple grammatical structures, making a coherent statement.

It is necessary to create a positive psychological attitude towards a foreign language in preschool children, and the method of creating such a positive motivation is a game. Children's ability to believe in their abilities in play activities allows to give a natural impetus to speech in a foreign language, to make even the simplest expressions interesting and meaningful. In teaching a foreign language, game activity does not contradict the educational activity, but is organically connected with it.

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